

Variational Quantum-Classical Optimization for Molecular Feature Generation: A Hybrid Machine Learning Approach

Abiodun Sojobi*¹

¹University of Lagos, Nigeria

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Abstract

The development of hybrid quantum-classical algorithms for complex chemical and biological simulations has been accelerated by the arrival of Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) devices. In this paper, we propose a prototype hybrid quantum-classical machine learning framework designed for molecular feature generation, targeting applications in drug discovery. Our model optimizes a continuous latent representation of a molecular state by minimizing a proxy for quantum mechanical binding energy evaluated via a Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)-inspired ansatz. The classical PyTorch neural network, which maps stochastic noise to bounded molecular features is bridged with parameterized PennyLane quantum circuit by the architecture. We employ a 4-qubit strongly entangling ansatz and utilize the parameter-shift rule to compute exact quantum gradients, enabling end-to-end differentiable optimization of both classical and quantum parameters. The hybrid pipeline successfully minimizes the expectation value of a multi-qubit Pauli-Z Hamiltonian towards its theoretical lower bound leveraging the joint gradient descent. We discuss the implications of this proof-of-concept for exploring vast chemical spaces and address the current challenges and scalability requirements for realizing practical quantum-enhanced drug discovery pipelines. All code and trained models are publicly available.

Keywords: quantum machine learning, variational quantum eigensolver, hybrid quantum-classical algorithms, drug discovery, molecular feature generation

1 Introduction

The process of discovering and developing novel pharmaceuticals is capital-intensive, and most times costs billions of dollars and takes over a decade of research. A significant bottleneck in this pipeline is the computational complexity of accurately simulating molecular interactions and predicting the binding affinities of drug candidates to biological targets [1]. Due to the complexity of computation, Classical computational chemistry methods, such as molecular dynamics and density functional theory (DFT), face scaling limitations in the process of solving the electronic structure of large molecules.

Quantum computing offers a new way to simulate the behavior of atoms and molecules specifically in computational chemistry. Feynman’s original proposition, that simulating quantum systems requires quantum hardware, has driven the search for algorithms capable of calculating molecular ground states with chemical accuracy [2]. The current era of Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) technology [3] has seen the rise of Variational Quantum Algorithms (VQAs) [4] even while fault-tolerant quantum computers fundamentally remain a long-term goal. Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE) [5], among many others, has emerged as the flagship algorithm for

*asojobi@unilag.edu.ng

the near-term quantum chemistry. Specifically, VQE leverages a parameterized quantum circuit (ansatz) to prepare a trial wavefunction and makes use of a classical optimizer to reduce the expectation value of the molecular Hamiltonian.

Quantum Machine Learning (QML) field simultaneously has sought to integrate the power of quantum circuits with the robust training paradigms of classical deep learning [6]. Hybrid quantum-classical networks utilize the strengths of both platforms: quantum circuits excels at modelling highly correlated states and exploring exponentially large Hilbert spaces efficiently, while classical networks performs excellently well at data compression and feature extraction.

In this study, we present a prototype hybrid quantum-classical machine learning framework for molecular feature generation. Our model aims to optimize a continuous latent representation of a molecular state, with inspiration drawn from generative adversarial networks (GANs) and VQE. We evaluate the quality of the generated features by a quantum circuit that computes a simplified proxy for binding energy, instead of relying solely on classical heuristics. By making the entire pipeline end-to-end differentiable using the parameter-shift rule [7], we optimize both the classical neural network weights and the quantum circuit parameters concurrently.

2 Methodology

The proposed architecture establishes a fully differentiable interface between a classical neural network and a parameterized quantum circuit. The objective is to map random noise into a bounded feature space such that the resulting features minimize a target Hamiltonian, when embedded into a quantum state.

2.1 Classical Parameterization

The classical component of the model operates as a feature generator. We employ a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) implemented in PyTorch [8]. The network takes a stochastic noise vector $z \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ of dimension \mathbb{R}^4 as input. The MLP consists of three fully connected hidden layers with the following dimensions $[4] \rightarrow [16] \rightarrow [32] \rightarrow [4]$.

After the first two layers, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activations are applied to ensure non-linear transformations. A Sigmoid activation function is strictly applied at the output layer. This bounds the generated molecular features f_i within the interval $[0, 1]^4$. Bounding the features is a critical step, as these values will be directly translated into rotation angles for the quantum embedding layer, and unbounded values can lead to periodic ambiguities and inefficient optimization.

2.2 Quantum Ansatz and Embedding

The generated features $f \in [0, 1]^4$ are passed to a quantum circuit simulated using PennyLane [9]. To process the information, we utilize a 4-qubit system and a strongly entangling ansatz.

The quantum circuit is structured in three distinct layers:

1. **State Preparation (Embedding):** The classical features f are encoded into the quantum state using parameterized Pauli-Y rotations. We apply the gate $R_y(\theta_i)$, for each qubit $i \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, where $\theta_i = f_i \cdot \pi$. This angle embedding strategy ensures that the entire $[0, 1]$ range of the classical output maps distinctively to a rotation between 0 and π on the Bloch sphere.
2. **Entangling Layer:** We apply a cascade of Controlled-NOT (CNOT) gates to generate highly correlated multi-qubit states. The entanglement topology is a ring structure: CNOT(0 \rightarrow 1), CNOT(1 \rightarrow 2), CNOT(2 \rightarrow 3), and CNOT(3 \rightarrow 0).

3. **Variational Layer:** The final layer consists of trainable Pauli-X rotations, $R_x(w_i)$, applied to each qubit i . The weights w_i are the free parameters of the quantum circuit that are updated during the optimization loop.

Figure 1: Visual representation of the 4-qubit quantum binding evaluator circuit. The architecture includes Pauli-Y state preparation based on the classical features, a CNOT entangling ring, and Pauli-X variational rotations.

2.3 Hamiltonian Evaluation and Loss Function

In a full quantum chemistry simulation, the Hamiltonian would be derived from the second-quantized fermionic operators of the target molecule mapped to Pauli strings via transformations such as Jordan-Wigner or Bravyi-Kitaev. For this proof-of-concept, we define a simplified proxy Hamiltonian consisting of a global Pauli-Z tensor product:

$$H = Z_0 \otimes Z_1 \otimes Z_2 \otimes Z_3 \quad (1)$$

The quantum circuit measures the expectation value of this Hamiltonian with respect to the prepared parameterized state $|\psi(f, w)\rangle$:

$$E(f, w) = \langle \psi(f, w) | H | \psi(f, w) \rangle \quad (2)$$

This expectation value serves as our loss function, analogous to a binding energy proxy. The theoretical minimum of this expectation value is -1.0 .

2.4 Optimization via the Parameter-Shift Rule

A defining feature of modern hybrid architectures is the ability to train them end-to-end. Obtaining gradients of the quantum circuit output with respect to its inputs (both f and w) requires special treatment, unlike the gradients of the classical MLP which are computed using standard backpropagation via PyTorch’s ‘autograd’.

We utilize the parameter-shift rule [7, 10], which states that for any quantum gate generated by a Pauli operator, the exact analytical gradient of an expectation value E with respect to a parameter θ can be evaluated macroscopically by shifting the parameter:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta} = c [E(\theta + s) - E(\theta - s)] \quad (3)$$

where s is a macroscopic shift (typically $\pi/2$) and c is a multiplier.

This rule allows the classical optimizer to seamlessly backpropagate the error signal from the quantum measurement through the quantum state and back into the weights of the classical MLP. Both the classical MLP parameters and the quantum variational weights w are jointly optimized using the Adam optimizer [11].

3 Experiments and Results

We trained the hybrid pipeline for 150 epochs using a learning rate of 0.01 for both the classical and quantum Adam optimizers. The quantum circuit is simulated using PennyLane’s `default.qubit` backend.

The classical network learns to shape the random noise distribution, during training, into specific feature vectors f . Simultaneously, the quantum circuit adapts its variational parameters w in order to minimize the expectation value of the proxy Hamiltonian given the incoming state preparation.

In the early epochs, the optimization curve (Figure 2) demonstrates rapid convergence. The joint optimization successfully minimizes the expectation value E towards the theoretical lower bound of -1.0 . Because the pipeline is end-to-end differentiable, the classical network efficiently learns the inverse mapping required to prepare the optimal initial states for the quantum circuit, highlighting the synergy of the hybrid approach.

Figure 2: Convergence of the hybrid quantum-classical optimization loop. The expectation value of the proxy Hamiltonian reaches the theoretical minimum of -1.0 within 150 epochs.

We validate the computational pipeline by the successful minimization: stochastic noise is transformed into deterministic classical features successfully, which are then optimally embedded and processed by a parameterized quantum circuit to find a distinct energetic minimum.

4 Discussion and Limitations

This work demonstrates the feasibility of an end-to-end differentiable quantum-classical pipeline for feature optimization. The refined training machinery of classical deep learning can be utilized by treating the quantum circuit as a differentiable node within a larger computational graph.

However, we acknowledge several limitations of this prototype, when considering its application to real-world drug discovery:

1. **Simplified Hamiltonian:** The use of a simple $Z^{\otimes 4}$ operator is actually a proxy. Real molecular systems require the evaluation of Hamiltonians with a large number of non-commuting Pauli strings, which in turn significantly increases the measurement overhead on NISQ devices.
2. **Qubit Count and Scalability:** A 4-qubit system is basically too scanty for representing chemically relevant molecules. Although, scaling the number of qubits introduces bottlenecks like barren plateaus in the optimization landscape [12], where the variance of the gradients vanishes exponentially with the number of qubits.
3. **Data Representation:** The input is currently stochastic noise, and the output features are abstract vectors. To ground the latent space in actual chemical data, realistic molecular representations should be integrated by future iterations such as RDKit descriptors, SMILES strings, or molecular graphs.

The architecture provides a robust template, despite these limitations. Such hybrid pipelines will be critical for integrating quantum computational chemistry directly into generative drug design workflows, as quantum hardware scales and error mitigation techniques improve.

5 Conclusion

We have presented a prototype hybrid quantum-classical machine learning framework that optimizes molecular features by minimizing a quantum expectation value. We achieved exact end-to-end differentiable training, by combining a PyTorch-based neural network with a PennyLane quantum circuit and utilizing the parameter-shift rule. The model successfully converges to the theoretical energy minimum of the specified proxy Hamiltonian. While the current implementation operates on a simplified 4-qubit scale, it establishes the fundamental software architecture necessary for future, scalable quantum-enhanced drug discovery platforms. The code for this prototype is publicly available at <https://github.com/baysquire/hybrid-vqe-drug-discovery>.

Declarations

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Data and Code Availability: The code and pre-trained models required to reproduce the results presented in this paper are publicly available in the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/baysquire/hybrid-vqe-drug-discovery>) and archived on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19897386).

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